

EXPRESSIONS OF BASIC FIBROBLAST GROWTH FACTOR IN THE PEPTIC ULCER HEALING DUE THE NONSTEROIDAL ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Basic Fibroblast Growth Factor (bFGF) or FGF2 is the most active angiogenic peptide and plays important role in the pathogenesis of ulcers healing. High levels of bFGF have been describing in healing ulcer in gastrointestinal (GI) or systemic disease. However, its role in the phase of peptic ulcer especially at NSAIDs user remains limited data in human. This study was to know the expressions of bFGF in the process of NSAID-induced peptic ulcer healing.

Method: Peptic ulcer biopsies were processed for immunohistochemical staining characterization from 46 patients with a history of NSAIDs consumption and upper GI bleeding. Expression of bFGF was quantified as semiquantitative scoring of the positive stain as a whole (from 0-+3). Phase evaluation of healing peptic ulcer (Active=A), Healing=H, Cicatrix=C) by Sakita and Fukotomi endoscopy classification.

Results: Twenty-seven (58,7%) subject were male patient, mean age 61 ± eight years and most frequently consumed NSAIDs are meloxicam (12/26,1%). Majority of the subject was inactive (A) phase of peptic ulcer healing (27/58,7%). Expression of bFGF was significantly higher in patients with A phase (2.4±0,5) compared with H and C Phase (1.2±0.4; 0.4±0.5 respectively; p<0.001).

Conclusion: Increased expressions of bFGF inactive phase of peptic ulcer while the decline in phase of healing and cicatrix patients with NSAID, confirms it's crucial role in pathogenesis healing of the peptic ulcer.

KEYWORDS bFGF, Peptic ulcer, NSAIDs

Abbreviations

- bFGF - Basic Fibroblast Growth Factor
- COX - cyclooxygenase

- DAB - Diaminobensidine
- EGF - Epidermal Growth Factor
- FGF2 - Fibroblast Growth Factor-2
- GF - growth factor
- HGF - Hepatocyte growth factor
- H pylori - Helicobacter pylori
- NSAIDs - Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs
- PBS - phosphate buffered saline
- PDGF - Platelet Derived Growth Factor
- PG - prostaglandins
- TGF - Transforming growth factor
- TP - peptic ulcer
- Ugie - Upper Gastrointestinal Endoscopy
- VEGF - Vascular endothelial growth factor.

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Introduction

Peptic ulcer disease (TP), a gastric and duodenal ulcer, is a disease frequently found among old patients aged 60 years old and over [1,2]. Peptic ulcers are caused by an imbalance between aggressive factors consisting of endogenous factors (hydrochloric acid, pepsinogen/pepsin and bile salts) and exogenous factors (drugs and bacterial infections *H. Pylori*) with mucosal protective factors (the production of prostaglandins, gastric mucus, bicarbonate, growth factors and mucosal blood flow) [3,4].

One of the main causes of TP and recurrence of ulcers is nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) [5,6]. Data regarding hospital-based endoscopy gastrointestinal complications resulting from the use of NSAIDs in Indonesia varied and were relatively high in some areas such as in Makassar 71%, 67.7% Jakarta, Surabaya 61%, and Malang 21% [7]. The NSAID-induced pathomechanism of TP is based on the inhibition of the synthesis of prostaglandins (PGs) through a reaction catalysed by the cyclooxygenase (COX) enzyme [4]. During the administration of NSAIDs, the growth of new cells in the ulcer margin and improvements in basic ulcer angiogenesis experienced a disorder causing noticeable deceleration of ulcers healing [8]. One of the mechanisms is that NSAIDs inhibit the onset of angiogenesis due to local changes in the expression of angiogenic growth factors [8].

Basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF) is a glycoprotein with the ability to improve and accelerate the healing process of angiogenesis in a variety of tissue damage. The basic fibroblast growth factor is produced by mast cells and endothelial [9]. This protein is found in the brain, heart, kidney, adrenal gland, small intestine and colon of normal human as well as in gastric and colon. This protein, along with other growth factors, contributes to the process of angiogenesis in various damaged organs [10]. Basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF) or FGF2 is the most active angiogenic peptide [11] and plays an important role in ulcers healing [9,12,13]. These molecules are stored in the basement membrane or extracellular matrix and released in active form to stimulate tissue repair and healing [11]. The expression of these growth factors and receptors increases during the wound/ulcer healing and declines after the healing [14].

Several previous studies reported that bFGF accelerates wound healing in the intestinal epithelium and heals ulcers in experimental animals. Experimental studies on rats indicate that bFGF expression increased in gastric and duodenal ulcers but experienced a decrease in the post-healing [9]. Other studies have found that the concentration of bFGF showed an upward in the gastric mucosa with ulceration when compared with normal mucosa [15]. The data on bFGF expression in TP mostly come from experimental animals without single research to assess the expression of bFGF in the healing phase TP, causing NSAIDs, especially in Indonesia.

Material and Methods

This observational research was conducted at the Hospital Dr Wahidin Sudirohusodo in Makassar in Indonesia from October to December 2018. The method applied in the study was a cross-sectional design. The research was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, University of Hasanuddin Makassar Indonesia with the reference number: 850/UN4.6.4.5.31/PP36-KOMETIK/2018.

a. Population

Subjects were within the age of 18-75 years old, with a history of consumption or under the therapy of non-selective NSAIDs over the last >4 weeks with upper gastrointestinal bleeding or a history of gastrointestinal bleeding. Peptic ulcer diagnosis and biopsy with an examination of Upper Gastrointestinal Endoscopy/Esophago-gastro-duodenoscopy using Olympus instruments-Exera II GIF. The Overview of the phase of ulcer healing by endoscopic classification of Sakita and Fukotomi (1971) was comprised of the active phase (Ulcers covered with a layer of slime and the edematous edge), healing phase (Ulcers with <50% epithelial regeneration, with or without a closed wall) and cicatrix phase (Ulcer scars in red or white with surrounding rough epithelium and without cracked mucosa.) [16].

b. Methods and Data Collection

Helicobacter pylori examination by Giemsa examination was performed on the results of the biopsy, while bFGF expression examination was carried out using the immunohistochemistry method with a semiquantitative scoring system by histopathology. Staining epital cells, lamina propria, smooth muscle and mucous muscularis were calculated from 0-3 where bFGF + 3: bFGF staining was strong, bFGF + 2: medium staining, bFGF was easily visible, bFGF + 1: weak colouring, but bFGF was seen, and bFGF 0: no bFGF staining.

Procedure on bFGF Examination:

First of all, paraffin blocks were cut, using a microtome, with a thickness of 3-4 μ before dipped into the water bath. Pieces of tissue are collected with slides before drained. Afterwards, the code was written, using pencil, on the slide found on the paraffin block before it was heated on the hot plate for 1 hour. Next, the slide was refrigerated and stored in the basket prior to the process of deparaffinization (Xylol I, Xylol II, Xylol III) for 5 minutes respectively before rehydrated (Alcohol 96%, Alcohol 80%, Alcohol 70%) for 5 minutes. Subsequently, the slide was washed with tap water for 5 minutes before the basket containing the slide was stored in the decloaking contained by a solution of the Antigen retrieval decloaking chamber. Thereupon, the slide was placed in the rack holder and transferred to decloaking. The decloaking was closed and set for 40 minutes at a temperature of 95 degrees. After the thermal process, decloaking was set to release heat by removing the slides and stored at average-room temperature. After the temperature is reduced, decloaking is washed in 2x phosphate buffer saline (PBS) solution for 5 minutes. Slides are marked by carving circles around the network before adjusting to the slide tray. The following step is to remove them from the water before storing the slides in the endogenous peroxide blocking solution. Next, the slides were incubated for 15 minutes, washed with PBS 2x for 5 minutes, and taken one by one before dropped with a sniper background and soaked for the second time in 30 minutes. Afterwards, the sniper background solution was removed by draining it on the tissue. PBS 2x was washed for 5 minutes, dropped by Primary Antibody (bFGF), and incubated for 1 hour at average room temperature. PBS 2x was washed for 5 minutes, followed by Trekkie Universal, and left for 30 minutes. Furthermore, 2x PBS was drained on the tissue, Trekkavidin-HRP was pressed, and left for 30 minutes. 2x PBS was washed by soaking the slide for 5 minutes. During the washing process, diaminobenzidine (DAB) solution is made by mixing DOM chromogen one drop + 1 ml buffer substrate (mixed in a clean tube). Next, DAB was dropped onto

Table 1 Characteristics of the subjects (n = 46).

Variables		n	%
Gender	Man	27	58.7
	Woman	19	41.3
Age	<65 years	34	73.9
	≥ 65 years	12	26.1
Peptic ulcer healing	Active	27	58.7
	Healing	11	23.9
	Sikatriks	8	17.4
Expression of bFGF	0	5	10.9
	+1	12	26.1
	+2	17	37.0
	+3	12	26.1
NSAID type	Diclofenac 50 mg	9	19.6
	Phenylbutazone 200 mg	4	8.7
	Piroxicam 20 mg	8	17.4
	Meloxicam 15 mg	12	26.1
	Ketoprofen 100 mg	5	10.9
	Aspirin 100 mg	3	6.5
	Phenylbutazone + Prednisone	5	10.9

Table 2 Expression of bFGF in the phase of peptic ulcer healing.

Healing Ulcers	n	median	mean	SD	P
Active phase	27	2.0	2.4	0.5	0,000
Phase Healing	11	1.0	1.2	0.4	
Sikatriks	8	0.0	0.4	0.5	

the tissue, and observations are made. The tissue was observed until browned before soaked for 5 minutes with hematoxylin Meyer and washed with running water for 5 minutes. The tissue was dehydrated with Alcohol (Alcohol 70%, Alcohol 80%, Alcohol 96%) 5 minutes each before clearing (Xylol I, Xylol II, Xylol III). The slides were dried, dropped with the top of the object, and covered with a glass deck before being observed on a microscope [15].

c. Statistical Analysis

SPSS version 22 was used for the data analysis. Descriptive statistics, frequency distributions, Chi-Square and the Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to determine the assessment. The test results were significant if the p-value was <0.05.

Results

Of 46 subjects, 27 (58.7%) were males and 19 (41.3%) were females (table 1). The average age in this study was 61 ± eight years, with the highest age group at <65 years (73.9%). The most frequently nonselective NSAIDs was meloxicam (26.1%), while the least was aspirin (6.5%). Based on the endoscopic examina-

tion, bFGF scoring +2 (37.0%) was the most common expression. The most common part of the peptic ulcer healing was found in the active phase (58.7%). The quantity comparison of bFGF expression, according to the healing phase of peptic ulcer (Table 2), was determined significant, in which the highest level occurred in the active phase (2.4) while the lowest was found in the cicatrix (0.4) with p <0.001. The pattern of decreasing the quantity of bFGF expression from the active phase, healing phase and cicatrix is described in Figure 1.

Discussion

Previous studies on TP healing mostly focused on gastric acid secretion and mucosal protection. However, The current researches, from the point of view of wound healing, focus on the growth factors such as epidermal growth factor (EGF), transforming growth factors (TGF), fibroblast growth factors (FGF), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF) in the process of healing ulcers [14,17].

This study indicates that the proportion of male subjects was higher than that of females. This is by the metaanalysis of Hernandez et al. [18] and Aalykke et al. [19] which expressed that

Figure 1: The quantity of bFGF expression in the phase of peptic ulcer healing.

men had twice more significant risk than women from complications of a peptic ulcer due to NSAIDs where the risk increased along with age. Similar results were reported by Hamid et al. [20] of 52 NSAID-induced peptic ulcer patients in Pakistan, where there were 57.7% of men, with an average age of 59 years.

One of the most common side effects of NSAIDs is the effect of toxicity on the gaster, where monitoring of its use is an essential factor in the therapy of these drugs. Patients who have a high risk of complications in the gastrointestinal tract are patients ranging in age from ≥ 65 years, history of peptic ulcer, chronic disease, H. pylori infection, use of two or more NSAIDs simultaneously, therapy with antiplatelet, anticoagulant, and corticosteroids. [24] This study showed that the most age group was in the age group <65 years (73.9%), while the average age of subjects was $61 \pm$ eight years. This is in line with the study by Akil (2006) in Makassar on 1615 subjects with dyspepsia where the patients, mostly at the age of 45-65 years, disposed an esophagogastroduodenoscopy examination [1].

Based on the type of nonselective NSAID, the most consumed drug by the subjects in this study was meloxicam, which was 26.1%, while the least was aspirin 6.5%. A similar study was also reported by Hamid et al. [20] in 52 NSAID-induced peptic ulcer patients in Pakistan, where the most consumed drugs were non-selective NSAIDs in the form of diclofenac 33%, while naproxen was the least (4%). Meanwhile, the Antappan et al. in India who assessed the prevalence of NSAID-induced GI toxicity risk found 105 patients taking nonselective NSAIDs with the highest 51.4% lornoxicam, and the least aspirin (2%). The pattern of prescribing NSAIDs in Indonesia in primary care for cases of pain is often in the form of meloxicam with sufficient drug availability. Meloxicam has 2-4 times the risk of relative complications of gastric toxicity [24].

Several studies have reported that bFGF accelerates wound healing in the intestinal epithelium and cures ulcers in experimental animals. Experimental studies in mice showed that bFGF expression increased in gastric and duodenal ulcers but declined after healing. [9] Biological activity of bFGF induces proliferation and migration of various mesenchymal cells for the process of angiogenesis in cells that are damaged or dead. [25] This study indicates that the quantity of bFGF expression in the

phase of healing of peptic ulcers shows significance where the highest is in the active phase (2.4) and the lowest in cicatrix (0.4) with a value of $p < 0.001$. The research of Hull et al. [15] also reported similar results that bFGF expression increased in the gastric mucosa of ulcers. This result is also by the study of Brzozowski et al. [22] that there is an increased expression of growth factors, during the healing process of ulcers caused by NSAIDs, such as EGF, HGF and bFGF in the surrounding/periphery of the ulcer but decreases after healing. In line with the study, Mizuki et al. [23] conducted a study of 37 peptic ulcer patients and found that bFGF expression increased during ulcers and decreased in the healing process. Basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF) is stored in the basement membrane or extracellular matrix and is released in an active form to improve ulcer recovery and healing. [23]

In conclusion, bFGF expression, during the process of an NSAID-induced ulcer healing, increases in the active phase but declines after healing.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there was no conflict of interest in this study. All cost in this study was covered by the author's funds.

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